

TABLE I—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL CHELATES WITH 4-IPMP

Method → Metal ↓	Half-integral	Point-wise calculation	
H(I)	6.40	6.39	$\log P K^H$
Cu(II)	5.10	4.75*	$\log K_1$
	4.00	4.04*	$\log K_2$
	9.10	8.79*	$\log \beta_2$
Ni(II)	4.30	4.32*	$\log K_1$
	3.40	3.33*	$\log K_2$
	7.70	7.65*	$\log \beta_2$
Co(II)	3.50	3.45	$\log K_1$
Zn(II)	3.13	3.09	$\log K_1$

* Method of Least Squares.

The data in Table I show that the order of stability is $\text{Cu} > \text{Ni} > \text{Co} > \text{Zn}$. This is in agreement with Irving-Williams order⁶.

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The Study of Mixed Pyrochlores

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COMPOUNDS with the pyrochlore structure having formula $\text{A}_2\text{B}_2\text{O}_7$ have been reported by workers.¹⁻⁶ In the present studies two new mixed pyrochlores have been studied by X-ray powder diffraction and infrared technique.

In the cubic pyrochlore structure the large A cations are coordinated by eight oxygen ions and the smaller B cations are octahedrally surrounded by six oxygen ions.

The procedure adopted in the preparation of the samples is the same as reported in the previous communication.⁷ The X-ray patterns were taken on philips X-ray diffractometer using Cu $K\alpha$ radiation filtered through nickel. The infrared spectra were recorded from 250–800 cm^{-1} using KBr pellets. The results of X-ray analysis are given in Table 1.

TABLE I

Formula	Colour	Radius ratio rX/rY	Phases present
YSmTi ₂ O ₇	white	1.35	Pyrochlore ($a = 10.121 \pm .005 \text{ \AA}$)
YDyTi ₂ O ₇	white	1.24	Pyrochlore ($a = 10.050 \pm .005 \text{ \AA}$)
YNdTi ₂ O ₇	pale bluish	1.44	Pyrochlore ($a = 10.140 \pm .005 \text{ \AA}$) + Nd ₂ Ti ₂ O ₇)

From Table 1. it is observed that YSmTi₂O₇ and YDyTi₂O₇ have pyrochlore structures while YNdTi₂O₇ showed two phases, major pyrochlore phase and minor noncubic Nd₂Ti₂O₇ phase. Recently Knop⁶ have reported the stability region extending from Ahrens radius ratio $r(\text{A}^{3+}) : r(\text{Ti}^{4+})$, of about 1.22 to 1.50 for pyrochlore titanates. Though YNdTi₂O₇ ($rX/rY = 1.44$) is within the stability limit reported by Knop *et al.*⁶ for pyrochlore titanates, it did not show only pyrochlore phase. (The heating temperature was 1350° for 5 hr).

The infra-red spectrum of YSmYi₂O₇ was quite identical with the spectra of pyrochlore titanates reported by Knop⁶. The main feature of the YSmTi₂O₇ spectrum in the region 300–700 cm^{-1} , is a strong band with a wide flat maximum exhibiting shallow fine structure peaks at 276, 380, 430, 445 and 540.

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